

Synthesis of 2,6,10,14-Tetramethylpentadec-1-ene by using *p*-Toluenesulphonylacetic Acid Methyl Ester

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p-Toluenesulphonylacetic acid methyl ester has been used as an active methylene compound for the synthesis of norphytene (7) by successive alkylations with rhodinyliodide (2) and 2-iodo-6-methyl-heptane in our general strategy ($C_{10} + C_1 + C_2$) followed by removal of carboalkoxy group and *p*-toluenesulphonyl group.

NORPHYTENE, identified as a useful synthone for the synthesis of phytone¹, can be converted to phytol isomers which was recently converted to vitamin E². This necessitated to devise new routes for norphytene starting with compounds having this isolated double bond. Such a strategy has been applied for the synthesis of norphytene from enamines³, meldrum's acid⁴, tosylmethylisocyanide⁴ and cyanoacetic ester⁵. We have now used *p*-toluenesulphonylacetic acid methyl ester as an active methylene compound for alkylation and for the addition of one carbon atom in a strategy ($C_{10} + C_1 + C_8$) and used it for the synthesis of norphytene 2,6,10,14-tetramethylpentadec-1-ene. The reaction sequence is given in Scheme 1.

p-Toluenesulphonylacetic acid methyl ester (1) was reacted with rhodinyliodide (2) in the presence of sodium methoxide in dry THF⁶, in molar proportions and refluxed for 7 h. Usual workup gave a residue which was triturated with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) to yield the ester (2; 15.79%). The filtrate was column chromatographed over basic alumina (grade I). The petroleum ether eluate gave the unreacted iodide (2). Elution with benzene furnished the pure monoalkylated derivatives (3: 49%; and based on recovery of the ester, 73.77%); ν_{\max} (liquid film) 1 740 (COOCH_3), 1 320 and 1 145 ($-\text{SO}_2-$) and 890 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{CH}_2$, exomethylene); δ (CCl_4), 0.93 (3H, d, J 6 Hz, CHCH_3), 1.58 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.35 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 3.58 (3H, s, COOCH_3), 3.82 (1H, m, $\text{C}_\alpha-\text{H}$), 4.58 (2H, s, $\text{C}=\text{CH}_2$), 7.27 (2H, dd, J 8 Hz, ArH) and 7.67 (2H, dd, J 2 Hz, ArH).

The second alkylation of 3 with 2-iodo-6-methyl-heptane (4) in presence of sodium methoxide in THF did not work and with sodium hydride in THF under reflux for 12 h gave poor yield (5%) of the dialkylated product (5). In order to improve the yield of the dialkylated product (5), alkylation was tried under phase transfer catalyst (PTC) using solid KOH and tetrabutylammonium iodide as a phase transfer catalyst in THF as a solvent. But we could not get better yield of 5. Further, alkylation of 3 was carried out in dry HMPA using sodium hydride at room temperature (25°) for 48 h. Usual workup gave the dialkylated product in 33% yield. When the reaction mixture was stirred at 60° for 48 h, the dialkylated product was obtained in 40% yield. It was isolated by column chromatography over basic alumina (grade I) as above for the monoalkylated derivative (2).

Chromatographically pure 5 showed ν_{\max} (liquid film) 1 740 (COOCH_3), 1 320 and 1 145 ($-\text{SO}_2-$) and 890 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{CH}_2$); δ (CCl_4), 0.89 (12H, 4s, $4 \times \text{CHCH}_3$), 1.61 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.39 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 3.6 (3H, d, COOCH_3), 4.6 (2H, s, $\text{C}=\text{CH}_2$), 7.3 (2H, dd, J 8 Hz, ArH) and 7.7 (2H, dd, J 8 Hz, ArH). The dialkylated product (5) on treatment with potassium acetate in wet DMSO⁷ at 150–60° for

Scheme 1

7-8 h gave **6** (90%). The chromatographically pure **6** showed no ir band at 1740 cm^{-1} , but it showed bands at 1320 and 1445 cm^{-1} , confirming the presence of *p*-toluenesulphonyl group. Its pmr spectra (CCl_4) displayed peaks at δ 0.78 (12H, 4s, $4 \times \text{CHCH}_3$), 1.69 (1H, s, $=\text{CHCH}_3$), 2.43 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 2.82 (1H, m, C_6-H), 4.64 (2H, s, $\text{C}=\text{CH}_2$), 7.33 (2H, dd, J 8 Hz, ArH), 7.8 (2H, dd, J 8 Hz, ArH).

In order to get norphytene (**7**) the *p*-toluenesulphonyl group was removed according to the reported procedure⁸. Usual workup followed by chromatography gave pure **7** (70%), b.p. $128-30^\circ/1.5\text{ mm}$; ν_{max} (liquid film) 890 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{CH}_2$, exomethylene) and 1630 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{CH}_2$); δ (CCl_4), 0.89 (12H, 2s, $4 \times \text{CHCH}_3$), 1.733 (3H, s, CH_3) and 4.7 (2H, s, $=\text{CH}_2$).

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